

Everyday Life Information Seeking and Theory of *Habitus*: In search for Everyday Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

Everyday life information seeking (ELIS) of a total of eight persons belonging to two different classes—lower class and middle class in the society have been studied with Diary method and Critical-incident technique with Micro-moment timeline interview for a period of over one month. The study reveals that level of education, type of occupation, material possession, friends circles, are the key factors in persons' ELIS. Social stratification enact a pivotal role in shaping the ELIS of people belonging to different classes of the society. The information-have group of people dominate the information -have-not group in different spheres of life. Lack of time-budget, cultural possession, leisure time are shaping the ELIS of different persons in the society.

Keywords: Everyday life information seeking, Critical incident technique, Social stratification, Information searching, Society

INTRODUCTION

Human beings generate and consume a huge amount of information in day-to-day life. Information seeking (IS) of person creates the impetus for seeking two types of information viz. professional that is entirely job-related or occupation related and non-professional that is information which one needs in order to keep oneself abreast in everyday life. Unfortunately, though one consume a major amount of information in daily life by seeking non-professional information such as seeking doctors and medicine related information; seeking travel and tourism related information; information regarding zodiac, astrology, entertainment etc., this

domain of information seeking takes a long time to experience the treading of the researchers of information seeking and information scientists. Everyday life information seeking (ELIS) deals with this non-professional information seeking (Savolainen, 1995) of persons in daily life. While Pierre Bourdieu (1985 as cited in Grenfell, M. 2012) is of the opinion that practices are generated by the habits and so all practices after evidence of the structures of the habitus generate them, Savolainen (1995) thinks everyday life information seeking (ELIS) paves the ways by which an individual monitors daily events and seek information to solve specific problems and these ways are determined by values, attitudes, and interests characteristics of their way of life. Bordieu (1985) argued that in order to understand interactions between people, or to explain an event or social phenomena, it is insufficient to look at what is said, or what happens. However, it is necessary to examine the Social Space (Bourdieu, 1985 as cited in Grenfell, M. 2012) in which interactions, transactions and events occur in everyday reality which is an organised and ordered reality (Berger & Luckmann, 1979). 'Habitus' of Bordieu is central to his distinctive sociological approach and it is intended to transcend a series of deep-seated dichotomies structuring ways of thinking about social world. Undoubtedly, likewise, theory of habitus and ELIS could be juxtaposed and regarded complement to each other since ELIS refers to the acquisition of various informational (both cognitive and expressive) elements which people employ to orient themselves in daily life or to solve problems not directly connected with the performance of occupational tasks (Savolainen, 1995) thereby, employing the commonsense-knowledge in everyday life (Berger & Luckmann, 1979).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

For a couple years, scientists (Savolainen, 1995; Spink & Cole, 2006a, 2006b; Davenport, 2010; Williamson et al., 2012; Given, 2002; Karlsson et al., 2012; Huotari & Chatman, 2001; Ooi & Liew, 2011) try to unfold the mysteries of ELIS of persons through a substantive number of quantitative as well as qualitative studies. However, the present study tries to find the answer of the following questions:

1. Is the theoretical framework of 'Way of Life' and 'Mastery of Life' of Reijo Savolainen(1995) basing on theory of habitus of Pierre Bordieu appropriate enough to reflect the ELIS of persons?
2. Does everyday knowledge reflect the perfect ELIS practice of a person in modern world?
3. Does social stratification have any impact on a person's ELIS?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory of Habitus and Pierre Bourdieu

'Habitus' is a concept that orients our ways of constructing objects of study, highlighting issues of significance and providing a means of thinking relationally about those issues. It is the link not only between past, present and future, but also between the social and individual objective and subjective structure (Berger & Luckmann, 1979, p. 40) and agency. Pierre Bourdieu's "cultural capital" refers to forms of knowledge, skills, education, and any advantages a person has which give him a higher status in society (Abraham, 2015). Further, forming same opinion as Bourdieu, Abraham (2015) goes on presenting his iconoclastic view that capitalist societies depend on a stratified social system, where the working class has an education suited for manual labour, and levelling out such inequalities would break down the system. Thus, the inequality of performance at school of children from different social class yielding 'success at school' is primarily due to the cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1985 as cited in Grenfall, 2012) they bring to the school, not the effect of their natural attitude. Bourdieu's work in its true sense emphasizes how social classes, especially the ruling and intellectual classes, reproduce themselves even under the pretence that society fosters social mobility, particularly through education (Abraham, 2015, p. 218). Talking about social stratification and its impact on the education of the children, Bourdieu opines that the social and cultural capital (Savolainen, 1995) accumulated in the ranks of upper classes get multiplied through the education system which, rather than level out the differences, enhances the inequalities of

the stratified social system (Paulo Freire, 1970; Ivan Illich, 1971 as cited in Abraham, 2015).

Sociology of Everyday Knowledge

Language, undoubtedly, is the medium of knowledge—tacit and/or explicit that one pursues and that he forms from careful coding and decoding of disseminated and received information in his daily life. The common objectivations of everyday life are maintained primarily by linguistic signification. Everyday life is, above all, life with and by means of the language one shares with his fellowmen (Berger and Luckmann, 1979). Each and every individual possess a stock of knowledge that he employs in his daily life when he encounters problem in deciphering some situations, or rather critical situations and this Mastery of Life in ones Way of Life (Savolinen, 1995) is possible when an individual is equipped with the proper sources of information. So one's interaction with others in everyday life is constantly affected by his common participation in the available social stock of knowledge or 'common-sense knowledge' (Berger & Luckmann, 1979, p. 37). In daily life, one constantly employs one's common-sense knowledge' whether to orient himself with the other occurrence of daily life or to solve some specific problems one has in his hands (Berger and Luckmann, 1979; Savolainen, 1995). The ordered reality of everyday life (Berger and Luckmann, 1979, p. 35) thus gets functional with the interference of everyday life information at appropriate time. Again, the judgement of appropriate knowledge in need in the stated circumstances gets filtered with their relevance at the appointed hours depending on the individual traits. Thus, the social distribution of knowledge begins with the simple fact that one does not know everything known to other fellowmen, and vice versa, and culminates in exceedingly complex and esoteric systems of expertise (Berger & Luckmann, 1979, p. 60).

Everyday Life Information Seeking

Everyday life is divided into sectors that are apprehended routinely, (Berger & Luckmann, 1979; Savolainen, 1995; Williamson, 2006), and others that present one with problems of one kind

or another. The world of everyday life (Baert, 1998) is structured both spatially and temporally (Berger & Luckmann, 1979). The organism and the society impose upon people and upon inner time, certain sequences of events that involve waiting (Berger & Luckmann, 1979; Dervin, 1992; Savolainen, 1995). The notion of 'first things first' (Berger & Luckmann, 1979) in the context of everyday life echoes, undoubtedly, the 'order of things' (Savolainen, 1995) in reality. Everyday life information seeking (ELIS) paves the ways by which an individual monitors daily events and seek information to solve specific problems and these ways are determined by values, attitudes, and interests characteristics of their way of life (Savolainen, 1995). Savolainen (1995) employs two concepts in elaborating ELIS such as "Way of Life" which refers to "order of things" that is based on the choices that individuals make in everyday life and in which "things" stands for various activities taking place in the daily life world and "Mastery of Life" which refers to "keeping things in order" through some "caring activity" for the order of things in the daily life. There are five types of everyday life information needs of the international students such as finance, health, news of one's home country, housing and entertainment (Sin & Kim, 2013). While a separate ELIS study based on the classic one of Savolainen is conducted on pregnant women, members of a self-help support group and preschool children (Carey, McKechni & McKenzie, 2001), in international students everyday life information seeking, the role and impact of social networking sites have been done recently (Sin & Kim, 2013). The study emphasizes on the types of information needs and the meeting of the needs through social networking sites (SNS) (Huataru & Chatman, 2001; Sin & Kim, 2013). The study concluded with important note that individuals with varying characteristics look for different types of information online (Savolainen, 1995; Howard, 2004; Halder, Ray & Chakraborty, 2010; Sin & Kim, 2013).

METHODOLOGY

A study has been carried out on eight participants who have been randomly selected from known sources and personal familiarity. These participants have been interviewed once for an average

time of one hour twenty minutes in the course of data collection for over a month period of time. Diary method has been followed as the medium of data collection technique along with questionnaire and Micro-moment time-line interview. Critical incident technique has been followed in order to collect flawless and minute data from the participants. The participants have been given a diary so that they can record their events of non-professional information seeking as much as possible.

ANALYSIS

Details of the participants are as follows

Table 1: Age

Participants	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Age	55	39	40	60	31	35	48	44

Table 2: Education

Participants	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Educational Qualification	VIII Passed	Illiterate	Illiterate	Illiterate	M.Sc. B.Ed.	Eleventh standard	M.A., B.Ed	Graduate

Table 3: Occupation

Participants	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Occupations	Farmer	Rickshaw puller	Domestic help	Domestic help	Business	Housewife	Teacher	Business

Table 4: Income

Participants	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Income	5000	4000	1500	3000	20000	12000	40000	15000

FINDINGS

Financial conditions shape a persons status in Indian society largely. Basing on the income, P1 (P for participant), P2, P3, P4 belong to the poorer sections of the society and as per Government of India guidelines, they belong to the Below Poverty Line (BPL) category. They have to struggle hard in order to keep their existence in the society. Since they possess a low income, their 'cultural capital' are very low that creates a serious problem from their seeking of non-professional information. On contrary, P5,

P6, P7, P8 though they are from different professional and social background, belong to the Above Poverty Line (APL) category and they accumulate much higher 'cultural capital' through which they constantly employ the Mastery of Life in their ELIS.

Two cluster of groups have been devised for the study.

The lack of proper financial condition creates different lifestyles in both the groups.

Table 5: Differences between Group A and B

Items	Group A	Group B
Working Hour	More than 12 hrs a day	Almost 6-7 hours a day
Leisure time	Less than 3-4 hours a day	More than 5-6 hours a day
Daily newspaper reading	Seldom	Daily 1-2 hrs
Goods in possession	Radio, TV with limited channels, low cost mobile phones, bicycle.	Motorbike, Bicycle, Colour TV with plethora of channels, Android smart-phones, Washing machine, Air-conditioner, etc. Laptop, Desktop.
Schooling of children	Mostly Government run schools	Mostly private English medium schools
Interests	TV Serial watching, listening to songs	Gathering travel related information, attending parties, clubs, watching movies etc.
Information searching sources	Mostly human sources, sometimes newspapers and other media	Internet, TV News, newspapers, friends and relatives, books, journals etc.

DISCUSSIONS

As Savolainen(1995) has theorized in course of seeking the ELIS channels and sources that people mostly use known sources of information from where he has ever been benefitted or rather

since the Way of Life circles round through some very common daily incidents people get confused or anxious whenever for any reason this circles get disrupted. Mastery of Life (Savolainen, 1995), common-sense knowledge (Berger and Luckmann, 1979) keeps this Way of Life dynamic, undisrupted.

ELIS of Group A and Group B

Since the participants of Group A belong to the BPL category, earn a minimum amount to spend livelihood, work hard day and night, get very less time as leisure, possess a minimal friend circle along with a few options to get information from outside world, they possess very low cultural capital that in fact impact their ELIS. They have to depend on human sources of information to get oriented in everyday life. Entropy seems very much present in their handling of information. They tend to believe the information they get from any sources with a very minimal option of filtering it. Participants in Group B, on the other hand, possess a huge cultural capital through which they get information pinpointedly. Their family members remain satisfied with the filtered information at hand since most of them possess the gadgets that connect them with the outside world through Internet and smartphones. They belong to either the learned society themselves or they maintain relationships with people who belong to this category. Their Mastery of Life depend on mostly the authentic information sources or at least they possess the educational background enough to filter the information at hand. Since they get enough time as leisure time, their non-professional information seeking does not get confined in printed sources of information only; instead they use internet, electronic information sources and at times human sources in order apply Mastery of Life or Common-sense knowledge so that their Way of Life is kept in motion.

Social Stratification and ELIS of People in Society

The class system refers to the classification of people based on their economic positions in society (Abraham, 2015, p.141). Educational level, type of occupation, material possession, house type, and lifestyles are used to classify people into classes.

Classes, Max Weber argued, are stratified according to their relation to production and acquisition of goods (Bhattacharya, 2013, p.903). Basing on these arguments, undoubtedly, the participants of Group A belong to the poor class of the society. They are devoid of the luxury that participants of Group B enjoy naturally. The former ones have to struggle hard in order to earn bread and butter for their family while the latter lead life in much satisfied manner comparatively. Social stratification for Group A members impact lot since the children of these families get estranged from mainstream of life and lack the proper sources of information that can keep their Way of Life continuing. They, eventually, belong to the information have-not group and due to these they lag behind the children of Group B belonging families who provide good amenities and education to their children. A line of demarcation still exists in between them. Travel related information, general knowledge, entertainment-kind of information, music information, medicine-related information are very common matter of interests in the participants of B group while these do not fascinate the participants of A group. Consequently, the children of B group participants are groomed better than those of A group participants since they possess much skill in handling information and enough educational background to decipher information at hand.

CONCLUSION

People belonging to different strata of the society, possess different educational qualification, earn different amount of money, possess different material objects employ different technique in their ELIS. Those who belong to the upper class, upper-middle class or middle class of the society are better in handling information since they possess much gadgets to get oriented with the information in their daily life. However, the people who belong to the lower section of the society, earn less, get a few hours as leisure time lack the proper skill of handling information at hand. The illiterate people have to depend on other human sources of information or audio-visual media of information in order to apply their Mastery of Life on their Way of Life. Children belonging to different families of lower classes and middle or

upper-middle classes possess different skills of searching their non-professional information. They information-have group i.e. B group groom their children in better manner than the people of A group, the information-have -not group. Their level of anxiety and uncertainties regarding the information they get also differ since they belong to two different classes of the society.

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